

Unmanned aerial vehicle: a review and future directions

Mahmood A. Al-Shareeda¹, Murtaja Ali Saare², Selvakumar Manickam¹

¹National Advanced IPv6 Centre (NAv6), Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia

²Department of Computer Technology Engineering, Shatt Al-Arab University College, Basrah, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 2, 2022

Revised Jan 3, 2023

Accepted Jan 10, 2023

Keywords:

Drones

Flying ad-hoc network

Unmanned aerial vehicle

Unmanned aerial vehicle approaches

Unmanned aerial vehicle simulator

ABSTRACT

The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) will be crucial in the next generation of wireless communications infrastructure. When compared to traditional ground-based solutions, it is expected that their use in a variety of communication-based applications will increase coverage and spectrum efficiency. In this paper, we provide a detailed review of all relevant research works as follows. This paper presents types of UAVs (e.g., wireless coverage, military, agriculture, medical applications, environment, and climate, and delivery and transportation), characteristics of UAVs (e.g., node density, altering system topology, node mobility, radio broadcasting mode, frequency band, localization, and power consumption and network lifetime), the application of UAVs (e.g., Multi-UAV cooperation, UAV-to-VANET collaborations, and UAV-to-ground tasks). Additionally, this paper reviews the routing protocols of UAVs (e.g., topology-based, position-based, heterogeneous, delay-tolerant networks (DTNs), swarm-Based, and cluster-based) and simulation tools (e.g., OMNeT++, AVENS, MATLAB, NS3, SUMO, and OPNET). The design and development of any new methods for UAVs may use this work as a guide and reference.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Selvakumar Manickam

National Advanced IPv6 Centre (NAv6), Universiti Sains Malaysia

11800 USM, Penang, Malaysia

Email: selva@usm.my

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their improved stability and endurance in many missions, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), often called drones, have garnered significant contributions in various civilian and military service disciplines [1]-[3]. UAV uses are developing significantly as a result of their cutting-edge utilization in the internet of things (IoT) and fifth-generation [4]. Over the past ten years, UAVs have been used for many different purposes, such as item prevention and tackling, general security, road surveillance, military application, a search of hidden or serious regions, within-door or out-door navigation, aerial tracing, post-disaster application, e-hospital, message changing, infrastructure administration, contingency, and crisis administration, load transport, logistics and wildfire controlling [5]-[8].

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are a type of pilotless aircraft that can take to the air and stay there without the help of a live person. They have a wider range of uses and are less expensive than manned frameworks in many situations [9], [10]. UAVs can be piloted from afar with the help of a ground-based control station (BS) and a remote power source. Self-control of UAVs is possible via autopilot and various sensors like global positioning systems and inertial measurement units (IMU) [11]-[13].

Particularly prominent e-commerce giants like Amazon, Google, DHL, and Walmart have invested

heavily in UAV technology [14], [15]. The rise of e-commerce has resulted in an increase in demand for expedited shipping options, which could have a major effect on consumer spending. As a result, e-commerce firms are investigating options to expedite shipping. On the flip side, retailers have a serious challenge in terms of providing last-mile delivery that is both cost-effective and efficient [16]-[18].

With their rapid and creative designs that guarantee last-mile delivery while being ecologically friendly, UAVs have emerged as viable solutions in this field. UAVs have many advantages, including quick and simple deployment, scalability and flexibility, self-organization, cost-effectiveness, and great maneuverability [19]-[22]. To carry a variety of payloads, such as communication devices, navigational aids, sensors, and cameras, UAVs come in a wide range of configurations, sizes, weights, ranges, and performance traits. UAVs can be divided into numerous categories based on features, including arrangement, engine kind, weighting, domain, and extent [23]-[26].

Nevertheless, a number of significant issues severely restrict UAV performance. Restriction of motion, restricted autonomy, and limited flight time are all examples of such constraints. Factors such as sensor accuracy, difficult weather, the size of the fixed-wing aircraft, and battery life all contribute to a short flight time. Multiple UAV vulnerabilities enhance the likelihood of being subjected to malicious attacks [27]-[29]. A number of works have been conducted to evaluate the UAVs' weaknesses, threats, and attacks, and they have offered workable methods to address these issues, such as the use of high-quality components, including motors, wings, batteries, and manufacturing materials. According to several studies, UAVs can discover the shortest route to their destination by using optimization algorithms [30]-[32].

Several start-up companies have emerged to meet the rising demand for agricultural UAVs on the market. Price-waterhouse-coopers predicts that the market for agricultural UAVs will reach \$32.4 billion by 2050, making up about 25% of the global UAV market (see Figure 1 for more details) [33]. Some of the most well-known UAV manufacturers are DJI, Parrot, Precisionhawk, AGEagle, and trimble navigation. Although many unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been developed and brought to market, there are still issues that need fixing before they can be used effectively in agriculture [34].

Top-tier innovations can be found in areas like precise positioning, navigation, controls, imaging, communications, sensors, materials, batteries, circuits, and motors. Some technologies (e.g., equipment development, nozzle controls, and big data) are necessary for UAV use, depending on the nature of the farming industry and the specifics of the UAV's mission. It isn't easy to provide comprehensive details on all UAV technologies. Therefore, this review paper aims to provide a deep understanding of the types of UAVs, the characteristics of UAVs, the application of UAVs, and the routing protocols of UAVs. Meanwhile, this paper presents simulation tools and the future directions of this paper.

The remainder of this work is arranged as follows. Section 2 shows types of UAVs. Section 3 presents characteristics of UAVs. Section 4 presents the application of UAVs. Section 5 presents routing protocols of UAVs. Section 6 presents simulation tools. Section 7 presents the future directions of this paper. Finally, section 8 concludes this paper.

2. TYPES OF UAV

This section classifies UAVs according to their application used. The type of UAV chosen for a given purpose must satisfy a number of criteria, including energy capacity, endurance, payload, and adherence to local laws. As shown below, Figure 1 shows a number of UAV types that can be used for classification. Figure 1(a) shown UAV as wireless coverage: directional antenna-equipped UAVs are employed to offer wireless communication for both outdoor and indoor customers in crowded areas or when worldly BSs are unavailable due to inclement weather [35], [36]. Figure 1(b) shown type of UAV as military: defense forces all around the world are using UAVs more frequently for a set of purposes, such as vulgarity, monitoring, network, attacks, and warfare as a result of ongoing developments in UAV technology [37]. Figure 1(c) shown UAV use in agriculture: UAVs are able to plant seeds and seedlings, harvest crops, and look for weeds and pests. They could drizzle crops more precisely than a regular bulldozer can as well [38]. Figure 1(d) shown UAV purposed to medical applications: UAV use has started to spread among emerging medical fields. When an unexpected natural disaster strikes, they are utilized for search and rescue, for the delivery of drugs, first aid supplies, and lab samples, as well as for remote telemedicine and teleradiology services [39]. Figure 1(e) shown UAV use in environment and climate: UAV applications in the mining industry [40], animal conservation [41], forest fire detection [42], and many more uses are all ways that UAVs can be utilized to benefit the environment.

Figure 1(f) shown UAV purposed to delivery and transportation: delivery food, medical supplies, household goods, packages, and ship resupply can all be transported with UAVs [43].

Figure 1. Types of UAV: (a) wireless coverage, (b) military, (c) agriculture, (d) medical applications, (e) environment and climate, and (f) delivery and transportation

3. FEATURES OF UAV

As presented in Figure 2, the major features of UAV are node consent, altering system topology, node mobility, radio propagation model, frequency band, localization, and power consumption and network lifetime [44], [45], as the following described. Node density: the density of node is the middle amount of UAVs per size. In comparison to other ad hoc networks like MANET and VANET, FANETs have a lower UAV node density. Depending on the goal of the UAV's mission, the node density can be changed. Changing network topology: due to the UAVs' quick movements, UAV network topologies frequently change. Under conditions of frequent topological fluctuation, possible FANET topologies include mesh and star topologies, where dynamic routing is required, and all UAVs directly communicate with the ground control station (GCS) [46], [47]. Mobility of node: one of the key characteristics of UAV is node mobility, which is much higher than that of VANET and MANET. Depending on the type of UAV, UAV speeds range from 30 to 460 km/h. This may result in problems such as interruptions, link failure, and more. Radio propagation model: any simulation or design of a communications system must include the network's radio propagation model. The most common and straightforward simulation model used in extensive simulations is the Friis free space model. Frequency band: UAV communication systems frequently employ unlicensed bands like 0.9 GHz and 2.4 GHz. Congestion may result from the use of these bands, though. The best results for UAV-to-Ground communications come from combining 5 GHz with IEEE 802.11a. Localization: because UAVs are fast and mobile and cause changes in network topology, FANETs use low-latency global positioning (GPS) to find them. Energy use and network lifetime: energy restrictions are a serious problem for ad hoc networks. The volume of the UAVs, the travel distances, the FANET's network technology, the link, and other obstacles all affect how much power is used in FANETs [48].

Figure 2. Characteristics of UAV

4. APPLICATION OF UAV

As shown in Figure 3, UAV has three primary applications that can be separated. The name of these applications as Multi-UAV cooperation, UAV-to-VANET collaborations, and UAV-to-Ground tasks. The description of these applications is provided as follows.

Multi-UAV cooperation: i) Situations of emergency: UAVs are employed in the building sector to assess the safety and track the development of structures. In many other emergency situations, as well as during emergencies where terrestrial base stations are down, UAVs can be utilized to temporarily extend wireless covering in cellular systems [49]; ii) Tracking and monitoring in disaster situations: UAVs can assist in determining the direction that a flood is moving and then forecast which buildings will be at risk of damage. Similar to this, they can be used for rescue efforts following earthquakes, recognizing collapsed buildings with a high concentration of people, such as hospitals and schools, in order to give these locations a higher priority in rescue operations [50]; iii) Target detection: UAVs can use target detection technology like thermal and vision cameras to find people and objects [51].

UAV-to-VANET collaborations: i) Route guidance: due to the great mobility of the vehicles in VANETs, routing is insufficient. In VANETs with UAV assistance, multi-hop relays are used to transport data between vehicles and UAVs. In VANETs, UAVs are utilized to improve routing and give route guidance [52]; ii) Data packet delivery: according to the paradigm of load-carry-and-delivery (LCAD), which involves using numerous UAVs, data is filled from the origin user and transmitted to the specialization user by UAVs, UAVs deliver packet data [53]; iii) Roadway traffic monitoring: use of UAVs is much quicker than sending in the incident commander’s car. Additionally, UAVs can be used to improve road safety by recording real-time recordings of various security events and situations in road networks[54].

UAV-to-ground tasks: i) Search and rescue missions: UAVs are essential for search and rescue operations (SAR). FANETs are thought to provide a huge advantage in ensuring public SAR missions, safety, and handling natural or man-made critics such as terrorism, overflow, cataclysm, forestry fires, and tsunamis, and checking the security of vital infrastructure, including utilities like force and sea; and ii) public and civilian applications: due to their advantages over ground-based infrastructure in terms of flexibility and cost, UAVs have been very deployed in a crowd and civilian area applications, particularly in the shape of little quadcopters.

Figure 3. Application of UAV

5. ROUTING PROTOCOLS OF UAV

Various groups of routing protocols at the layer of the network are presented for UAVs in this section. Figure 4 shows one potential classification of UAV routing protocols. The description of these routing protocols is provided as follows. Topology-based: topology-based hop-by-hop routing protocols use link-state informa-

tion like IP addresses and network topology information to help senders route packets in the most efficient way possible [55]. Position-based: these protocols use reactive, predictive, greedy [56], [57], and hierarchical [58] techniques to determine the transmitter and receiver's positions in advance utilizing the geographic information of the nodes known from GPS. Heterogeneous: different ground systems, such as MANETs, VANETs, or stationary users, with which FANETs communicate, require varied routing protocols in order to exchange data between moving users. In FANETs, both mobile and fixed nodes can be supported using routing protocols with heterogeneous approaches [59]. Delay-tolerant networks (DTNs): the mobile nodes in DTNs are sporadically and erratically connected. In order to handle the DTN features, new routing protocols are required because mobile nodes have high latency and low data throughput [44]. Swarm-based: this routing method uses fish, bird, and insect social behavior to discover the best path and topology management strategy [60]. Cluster-based: nodes with comparable traits and properties are merged to form clusters in the clustering approach. Each cluster has a cluster head, which handles communication processing [61].

Figure 4. Routing protocols of UAV

6. SIMULATION TOOLS

The process of assessing the effectiveness of the UAV-enabled system in the actual universe is challenging and takes a significant amount of time and money. The top class of mobility of the UAVs and the frequent topology changes makes it difficult, expensive, and time-consuming to evaluate UAV performance practically. Additionally, many forms of cyber-attack resistance estimation testing for UAV networks are prohibited due to rules surrounding the use of UAVs in the majority of nations [62]. Consequently, a variety of adaptable simulation tools have been created to enable the creation, construction, testing, and evaluation of schemes virtually without the need for practical application. The available FANET performance study tools include OMNeT++, AVENS, MATLAB, NS3, SUMO, and OPNET. Additional information on each simulator is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. UAV system performance study simulation tools

Name	Programming language	Mobility model	Operating system
OMNeT++	C++, high-level language (NED)	Flight plan (FP), random waypoint (RWP), random walk (RW)	Linux, MacOS. and Windows
AVENS	N/A	Linear mobility	Linux, Windows, MacOS
MATLAB	C, C++	Semi-random circular movement (SRCM), particle swarm mobility model (PSMM)	Windows, Linux, and MacOS
NS3	C++, with an OTcl interpreter	Random walk (RW), random waypoint (RWP), Gauss Markov (GM), reference point group mobility model (RPGM)	Linux, Windows, MacOS
SUMO	C++, Python	N/A	Windows, Linux or MacOS
OPNET	C, C++	Random direction (RD), random walk (RW), random waypoint (RWP), group mobility	Red Hat, Windows and CentOS

- OMNeT++: a component-based network simulator that uses the Windows language (NED) and is modular, extendable, and used both for academic and commercial applications.
- AVENS: a simulator-based control of flight that integrates co-simulation among modeling simulations using OMNeT++/INET and the XPlane flying simulator drone communication
- MATLAB: the capability to incorporate ML/AI with its docile and ML Toolbox, a UAV Toolbox, and

various sample applications using both fixed-wing and multirotor UAVs are also provided.

- NS3: both IP and non-IP networks can be simulated. The effectiveness of TCP and mobile ad hoc networks can be evaluated using it.
- SUMO: it can be combined with OMNeT and NS3, but since it is designed for 2D vehicles, it cannot be used directly in FANETs.
- OPNET: offers a strong graphical user interface with animated graphics considerable expenses.

7. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The problems with UAVs that were discussed earlier have been the subject of numerous proposals for acceptable solutions, but there are still many problems that need to be solved. This section discusses the future direction of UAVs. The following points are provided in detail.

- There are a number of advantages for different collaborative areas provided by collaborative UAV technologies; however, there are a number of issues that need to be resolved.
- Energy-efficient algorithms must be developed for various elements, including cooperative communication, sensing, processing, actuating, and data storage due to the energy limits of UAVs [63].
- Another difficult problem in UAV-assisted technologies are providing effective resource management techniques that attempt to dynamically make purse including bandwidth, broadcasting power, the number of UAVs, and its flight time.
- Given that UAVs are now frequently employed in communications, including domains (military, emergency services, and infrastructure search) that contain critical data, providing security in UAV-enabled communication is a challenging task. Therefore, reliable and secure communications and services in UAV-related technologies need to be provided through the use of efficient methods.
- The flexibility of a UAV's deployment depends on its mobility and its ability to fly to its destination and complete its mission. UAVs' ability to react and state their mobility in real time is critical for conflict avoidance and power management.

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

UAVs are used in a wide variety of applications nowadays. The applications of these systems are only briefly discussed in a small number of highly specialized research articles. By offering a general overview of the various uses of numerous UAV systems that have been created recently, this survey seeks to close this gap. This paper presents the types of UAVs, the characteristics of UAVs, the application of UAVs, the routing protocols of UAVs, and simulation tools. Additionally, we present the future directions of this paper. In future work, we will propose a scheme based on UAV to secure the VANET communication system in order to prevent any attacker as well as decrease the overhead of the system in terms of communication and computational costs.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. A. H. Mohsan, M. A. Khan, F. Noor, I. Ullah, and M. H. Alsharif, "Towards the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): a comprehensive review," *Drones*, vol. 6, no. 6, p. 147, 2022, doi: 10.3390/drones6060147.
- [2] P. McEnroe, S. Wang, and M. Liyanage, "A Survey on the convergence of edge computing and AI for UAVs: opportunities and challenges," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 17, pp. 15435–15459, 2022, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2022.3176400.
- [3] H. Pourrahmani, C. M. I. Bernier, and J. V. herle, "The application of fuel-cell and battery technologies in unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): a dynamic study," *Batteries*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. 73, 2022, doi: 10.3390/batteries8070073.
- [4] A. Srivastava and J. Prakash, "Internet of low-altitude UAVs (IoLoUA): a methodical modeling on integration of Internet of 'Things' with 'UAV' possibilities and tests," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10462-022-10225-1.
- [5] M. S. Alam and J. Oluoch, "A survey of safe landing zone detection techniques for autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs)," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 179, p. 115091, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2021.115091.
- [6] O. Balli and H. Caliskan, "On-design and off-design operation performance assessment of an aero turboprop engine used on unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in terms of aviation, thermodynamic, environmental and sustainability perspectives," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 243, p. 114403, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114403.
- [7] M. A. Al-Shareeda, S. Manickam, S. A. Laghari, and A. Jaisan, "Replay-Attack Detection and Prevention Mechanism in Industry 4.0 Landscape for Secure SECS/GEM Communications," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 23, p. 15900, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su142315900.
- [8] N. Elmeseiry, N. Alshaer, and T. Ismail, "A detailed survey and future directions of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) with potential applications," *Aerospace*, vol. 8, no. 12, p. 363, 2021, doi: 10.3390/aerospace8120363.

- [9] J. Zheng *et al.*, “Growing status observation for oil palm trees using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) images,” *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 173, pp. 95–121, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2021.01.008.
- [10] M. A. Jasim, H. Shakhathreh, N. Siasi, A. H. Sawalmeh, A. Aldalbahi, and A. Al-Fuqaha, “A survey on spectrum management for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs),” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 11443–11499, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3138048.
- [11] M. A. Al-Shareeda *et al.*, “Provably Secure with efficient data sharing scheme for fifth-generation (5G)-enabled vehicular networks without road-side unit (RSU),” *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 16, p. 9961, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14169961.
- [12] P. Velusamy, S. Rajendran, R. K. Mahendran, S. Naseer, M. Shafiq, and J.-G. Choi, “Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) in precision agriculture: applications and challenges,” *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 217, 2021, doi: 10.3390/en15010217.
- [13] M. A. Al-Shareeda and S. Manickam, “Man-in-the-middle attacks in mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs): analysis and evaluation,” *Symmetry*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 1543, 2022, doi: 10.3390/sym14081543.
- [14] R. Adade, A. M. Aibinu, B. Ekumah, and J. Asaana, “Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) applications in coastal zone management—a review,” *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 193, no. 3, p. 154, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10661-021-08949-8.
- [15] M. A. Al-Shareeda and S. Manickam, “COVID-19 vehicle based on an efficient mutual authentication scheme for 5G-enabled vehicular fog computing,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 23, p. 15618, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph192315618.
- [16] H. Chen, Y. Lan, B. K. Fritz, W. C. Hoffmann, and S. Liu, “Review of agricultural spraying technologies for plant protection using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV),” *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 38–49, 2021, doi: 10.25165/j.ijabe.20211401.5714.
- [17] P. Shilin, R. Kirichek, A. Paramonov, and A. Koucheryavy, “Connectivity of VANET segments using UAVs,” in *Internet of Things, Smart Spaces, and Next Generation Networks and Systems. ruSMART NEW2AN 2016 2016. Lecture Notes in Computer Science()*, Cham: Springer, 2016, pp. 492–500.
- [18] M. A. Al-Shareeda *et al.*, “Chebyshev polynomial-based scheme for resisting side-channel attacks in 5G-enabled vehicular networks,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 12, p. 5939, 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12125939.
- [19] M. A. Al-shareeda *et al.*, “Proposed efficient conditional privacy-preserving authentication scheme for V2V and V2I communications based on elliptic curve cryptography in vehicular ad hoc networks,” in *Advances in Cyber Security. ACeS 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 588–603.
- [20] O. S. Oubbati, N. Chaib, A. Lakas, P. Lorenz, and A. Rachedi, “UAV-assisted supporting services connectivity in urban VANETs,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 3944–3951, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2019.2898477.
- [21] S. M. Pournaghi, B. Zahednejad, M. Bayat, and Y. Farjami, “NECPPA: a novel and efficient conditional privacy-preserving authentication scheme for VANET,” *Computer Networks*, vol. 134, pp. 78–92, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2018.01.015.
- [22] M. A. Al-shareeda, M. Anbar, M. A. Alazzawi, S. Manickam, and I. H. Hasbullah, “Security schemes based on conditional privacy-preserving vehicular ad hoc networks,” *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 479–488, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v21.i1.pp479-488.
- [23] S. Schenone, M. Azhar, C. A. V. Ramirez, A. G. Strozzi, P. Delmas, and S. F. Thrush, “Mapping the delivery of ecological functions combining field collected data and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs),” *Ecosystems*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 948–959, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10021-021-00694-w.
- [24] M. A. Al-Shareeda and S. Manickam, “MSR-DoS: modular square root-based scheme to resist denial of service (DoS) attacks in 5G-enabled vehicular networks,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 120606–120615, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3222488.
- [25] H. Sedjelmaci, M. A. Messous, S. M. Senouci, and I. H. Brahmi, “Toward a lightweight and efficient UAV-aided VANET,” *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 30, no. 8, 2019, doi: 10.1002/ett.3520.
- [26] M. A. Al-Shareeda, M. Anbar, S. Manickam, and I. H. Hasbullah, “A secure pseudonym-based conditional privacy-preservation authentication scheme in vehicular ad hoc networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, p. 1696, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22051696.
- [27] H. S. Ndlovu *et al.*, “A comparative estimation of maize leaf water content using machine learning techniques and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based proximal and remotely sensed data,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 20, p. 4091, 2021, doi: 10.3390/rs13204091.
- [28] E. Shaikh, N. Mohammad, and S. Muhammad, “Model checking based unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) security analysis,” in *2020 International Conference on Communications, Signal Processing, and their Applications (ICCSPA)*, 2021, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICCSPA49915.2021.9385754.
- [29] M. A. Al-Shareeda, M. Anbar, S. Manickam, and I. H. Hasbullah, “Password-guessing attack-aware authentication scheme based on chinese remainder theorem for 5G-enabled vehicular networks,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 1383, 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12031383.
- [30] D. Cirillo, F. Cerritelli, S. Agostini, S. Bello, G. Lavecchia, and F. Brozzetti, “Integrating post-processing kinematic (PPK)-structure-from-motion (SfM) with unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) Photogrammetry and digital field mapping for structural geological analysis,” *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, vol. 11, no. 8, p. 437, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijgi11080437.
- [31] H. Shao *et al.*, “Assessing city-scale green roof development potential using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery,” *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, vol. 57, p. 126954, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126954.
- [32] M. A. Al-Shareeda *et al.*, “CM-CPPA: chaotic map-based conditional privacy-preserving authentication scheme in 5G-enabled vehicular networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, p. 5026, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22135026.
- [33] L. Brief, “Growth opportunity in global uav market,” Las Colinas, USA, 2011.
- [34] J. Kim, S. Kim, C. Ju, and H. Il Son, “Unmanned aerial vehicles in agriculture: a review of perspective of platform, control, and applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 105100–105115, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2932119.
- [35] A. Srivastava and J. Prakash, “Role of Antenna in flying adhoc networks communication: provocation and open issues,” in *Intelligent Systems Design and Applications. ISDA 2020. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, Cham: Springer, 2021, pp. 711–721.
- [36] H. Shakhathreh *et al.*, “Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): a survey on civil applications and key research challenges,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 48572–48634, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2909530.
- [37] A. Utsav, A. Abhishek, P. Suraj, and R. K. Badhai, “An IoT based UAV network for military applications,” in *2021 Sixth International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET)*, 2021, pp. 122–125, doi: 10.1109/WiSPNET51692.2021.9419470.

- [38] M. F. Aslan, A. Durdu, K. Sabanci, E. Ropelewska, and S. S. Gültekin, "A comprehensive survey of the recent studies with UAV for precision agriculture in open fields and greenhouses," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 1047, 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12031047.
- [39] H. C. de Resende, J. F. N. Pinheiro, P. Reiter, C. B. Both, and J. M. Marquez-Barja, "4G/5G performance of a multi-RAT UAV for medical parcel delivery," in *2022 IEEE 19th Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC)*, 2022, pp. 268–271, doi: 10.1109/CCNC49033.2022.9700528.
- [40] M. Loots, S. Grobbelaar, and E. van der Lingen, "A review of remote-sensing unmanned aerial vehicles in the mining industry," *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, vol. 122, no. 7, pp. 1–10, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.17159/2411-9717/1602/2022.
- [41] E. Corcoran, M. Winsen, A. Sudholz, and G. Hamilton, "Automated detection of wildlife using drones: Synthesis, opportunities and constraints," *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 1103–1114, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.13581.
- [42] A. Muid *et al.*, "Potential of UAV application for forest fire detection," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2243, no. 1, p. 012041, 2022, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2243/1/012041.
- [43] M. Golabi and M. G. Nejad, "Intelligent and fuzzy UAV transportation applications in aviation 4.0," in *Intelligent and Fuzzy Techniques in Aviation 4.0. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, Cham: Springer, 2022, pp. 431–458.
- [44] A. Srivastava and J. Prakash, "Future FANET with application and enabling techniques: Anatomization and sustainability issues," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 39, p. 100359, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cosrev.2020.100359.
- [45] M. M. S. Ibrahim and P. Shanmugaraja, "Optimized link state routing protocol performance in flying ad-hoc networks for various data rates of Un manned aerial network," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 37, pp. 3561–3568, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.09.543.
- [46] S. Kumar, R. S. Raw, and A. Bansal, "LoCaL: link-optimized cone-assisted location routing in flying ad hoc networks," *International Journal of Communication Systems*, vol. 36, no. 2, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1002/dac.5375.
- [47] S. Kumar, R. S. Raw, A. Bansal, M. A. Mohammed, P. Khuwuthyakorn, and O. Thinnukool, "3D location oriented routing in flying ad-hoc networks for information dissemination," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 137083–137098, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3115000.
- [48] S. Kumar, R. S. Raw, and A. Bansal, "Energy and direction aware routing protocol for flying ad hoc networks," in *Proceedings of International Conference on Communication, Circuits, and Systems. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 371–378.
- [49] E. Lekkas, E. Andreadakis, M. Diakakis, S. Mavroulis, and V. Antoniou, "Natural disasters: mapping and evaluating incidents," in *Emergency Medicine, Trauma and Disaster Management. Hot Topics in Acute Care Surgery and Trauma*, Cham: Springer, 2021, pp. 451–462.
- [50] R. Masroor, M. Naeem, and W. Ejaz, "Efficient deployment of UAVs for disaster management: a multi-criterion optimization approach," *Computer Communications*, vol. 177, pp. 185–194, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.comcom.2021.07.006.
- [51] J. Sun, B. Li, Y. Jiang, and C. Y. Wen, "A camera-based target detection and positioning UAV system for search and rescue (SAR) purposes," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 11, 2016, doi: 10.3390/s16111778.
- [52] K. Zhang, K. Li, J. He, H. Shi, Y. Wang, and C. Niu, "A UAV autonomous maneuver decision-making algorithm for route guidance," in *2020 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, 2020, pp. 17–25, doi: 10.1109/ICUAS48674.2020.9213968.
- [53] J. Yoon, A.-H. Lee, and H. Lee, "Rendezvous: opportunistic data delivery to mobile users by UAVs through target trajectory prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 2230–2245, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2019.2962391.
- [54] A. Bujari, C. T. Calafate, J.-C. Cano, P. Manzoni, C. E. Palazzi, and D. Ronzani, "Flying ad-hoc network application scenarios and mobility models," *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 155014771773819, 2017, doi: 10.1177/1550147717738192.
- [55] M. A. Khan, I. U. Khan, A. Safi, and I. M. Quershi, "Dynamic Routing in flying ad-hoc networks using topology-based routing protocols," *Drones*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 27, 2018, doi: 10.3390/drones2030027.
- [56] K. Singh and A. K. Verma, "Experimental analysis of AODV, DSDV and OLSR routing protocol for flying adhoc networks (FANETs)," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, 2015, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICECCT.2015.7226085.
- [57] J. Li, J. Jannotti, D. S. J. De Couto, D. R. Karger, and R. Morris, "A scalable location service for geographic ad hoc routing," in *Proceedings of the 6th annual international conference on Mobile computing and networking*, 2000, pp. 120–130, doi: 10.1145/345910.345931.
- [58] K. Singh and A. K. Verma, "Applying OLSR routing in FANETs," in *2014 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Communications, Control and Computing Technologies*, 2014, pp. 1212–1215, doi: 10.1109/ICACCCT.2014.7019290.
- [59] O. S. Oubbati, M. Atiquzzaman, P. Lorenz, M. H. Tareque, and M. S. Hossain, "Routing in flying ad hoc networks: survey, constraints, and future challenge perspectives," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 81057–81105, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2923840.
- [60] F. Fabra *et al.*, "MUSCOP: mission-based UAV swarm coordination protocol," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 72498–72511, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2987983.
- [61] M. Y. Arafat and S. Moh, "A survey on cluster-based routing protocols for unmanned aerial vehicle networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 498–516, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2885539.
- [62] A. Chriki, H. Touati, H. Snoussi, and F. Kamoun, "FANET: communication, mobility models and security issues," *Computer Networks*, vol. 163, p. 106877, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106877.
- [63] S. Kumar, N. K. Rathore, M. Prajapati, and S. K. Sharma, "SF-GoeR: an emergency information dissemination routing in flying Ad-hoc network to support healthcare monitoring," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12652-022-04434-3.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Mahmood A. Al-Shareeda obtained his Ph.D. in Advanced Computer Network from University Sains Malaysia (USM). He is currently a postdoctoral fellowship at National Advanced IPv6 Centre (NAv6), Universiti Sains Malaysia. His current research interests include network monitoring, internet of things (IoT), vehicular ad hoc network (VANET) security and IPv6 security. He can be contacted at email: alshareeda022@usm.my.

Murtaja Ali Saare is an Assistant Professor at the Department of Computer Technology Engineering, Shatt Al-Arab University College, Iraq. He received his master's degree in Information Technology at Universiti Utara Malaysia (UUM), in 2017. He completed his Ph. D at School of Computing, Sintok, UUM, Kedah, Malaysia, in 2021. His research interest includes aging and cognition, e-health, and human-centered computing. He has published his research work in reputable Scopus indexed journal. He can be contacted at email: mmurtaja88@gmail.com and murtaja.a.sari@sauc.edu.iq.

Selvakumar Manickam is currently working as an Associate Professor at National Advanced IPv6 Centre (NAv6), Universiti Sains Malaysia. His research interests include Cybersecurity, Internet of Things, Industry 4.0, and Machine Learning. He has authored and co-authored more than 160 articles in journals, conference proceedings, and book reviews and graduated 13 PhD. He has 10 years of industrial experience prior to joining academia. He is a member of technical forums at national and international levels. He also has experience building IoT, embedded, server, mobile, and web-based applications. He can be contacted at email: selva@usm.my.